

Design and control concept of a 1 MW_{th} chemical looping gasifier allowing for efficient autothermal syngas production

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ABSTRACT

Chemical looping gasification (CLG) is a novel gasification concept, allowing for the efficient production of a high calorific, N₂-free syngas with low tar content. Previous studies showed that the inherent process characteristics require a dedicated process control concept in order to allow for sufficient solid and thus heat transport between the two reactors (air and fuel reactor) of the gasification unit, while at the same time being able to accurately tailor the air-to-fuel equivalence ratio (λ), thus obtaining stable gasification conditions. To demonstrate its viability, a suitable control concept was implemented in the 1 MW_{th} modular pilot plant located at the Technical University Darmstadt. In this paper, results obtained during the first ever autothermal CLG operation, achieved in this unit using biomass pellets as the feedstock, are presented, highlighting important process fundamentals. It is demonstrated that the novel process control concept allows for an accurate control of λ in semi-industrial scale, while at the same time guaranteeing stable hydrodynamics and thus solid and heat transport between the air and fuel reactor, making it a suitable control concept for large-scale implementation. Moreover, it is demonstrated that the underlying phenomena of the CLG process lead to substantial system inertia, as the solid bed inventory of the gasifier acts as an oxygen storage during transient periods, evoked by changes in the air-to-fuel equivalence ratio.

1. Introduction

In light of the current challenges in terms of climate protection and energy transition, novel, sustainable and yet competitive processes and technologies in the energy, transport, and industry sector are urgently needed. Thus, innovative carbon-negative process chains for the production of 2nd generation biofuels are required (DIRECTIVE (EU) 2018). Here, one option under broad consideration is converting biogenic residues into a high-calorific syngas, before further treatment and fuel synthesis (Atsonios et al., 2020; Roshan Kumar et al., 2022).

Oxygen-blown gasifiers, allowing for the efficient production of a N₂-free syngas, thus facilitating its direct utilization in syntheses, have been widely researched, going back to the start of the last century (Higman and van der Burgt, 2008). With recent developments encouraging routes of valorizing residues (e.g. biomass, municipal waste, etc.) chemically, research interest in this field has been revived (Heinze et al., 2023; Langner et al., 2023). Apart from their maturity, the advantages of oxygen-blown gasifiers arise from the direct utilization of molecular oxygen in the gasification chamber, thus facilitating high reaction temperatures and excellent feedstock conversion. Therefore, cold gas

efficiencies above 75% can be obtained, depending on the gasifier type and the utilized feedstock (Higman and van der Burgt, 2008).

A novel gasification technology, allowing for an efficient conversion of biomass residues into a high-calorific syngas, is the chemical looping gasification (CLG) process, illustrated in Fig. 1. Its major advantage is that the oxygen required for efficient feedstock conversion is supplied through the cyclic reduction and oxidation of an oxygen carrier (OC). Hence, CLG does not rely on a costly air separation unit, commonly required for oxygen-driven gasification processes. Moreover, despite air being used as the oxygen source in the gasification process, CLG allows for an efficient capturing of the CO₂ formed during the autothermal gasification step from the N₂-free product gas in the downstream syngas purification unit, thus allowing for net negative CO₂ emissions of the biomass-to-biofuel process chain (Nguyen et al., 2021; Huang et al., Oct. 2016; Huang et al., Jan. 2014; Ge et al., 2016a; Guo et al., 2014; Huang et al., Jul. 2013).

Initial advances in the CLG were mainly restricted to lab-scale investigations. Here, the CLG technology was investigated in batch (Huang et al., Jan. 2014; Huang et al., Jul. 2013; Xu et al., Nov. 2021) as well as continuous reactor setups (Huseyin et al., 2014; Acharya et al., 2009), operated as fixed bed (Yan et al., May 2020; Liu et al., Nov. 2019)

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Nomenclature		Abbreviations/Acronyms	
<i>Latin Symbols</i>		AR	Air Reactor
d	Diameter	BP	Operating Period
l	length	CFB	Circulating Fluidized Bed Reactor
LHV	Lower heating value	CGE	Cold Gas Efficiency
m_i	Mass of species i	CLG	Chemical Looping Gasification
\dot{m}_i	Mass Flow of species i	CLC	Chemical Looping Combustion
\dot{n}_i	Mole Flow of species i	DFBG	Dual Fluidized Bed Gasification
P	Power	FR	Fuel Reactor
\dot{Q}_{cool}	Cooling Duty	LS	Loop Seal
RR	Recycling Ratio	MSR	Measurement and Control
R_{OC}	Oxygen transport capability	OC	Oxygen Carrier
R_{Feed}	Oxygen requirement of feedstock	TP	Transient Period
R_{C3H8}	Oxygen requirement of Propane		
T	Temperature	<i>Indices</i>	
u_0	Gas Velocity	AR	Air Reactor
$\dot{V}_{Rec.}$	Volume flow of recycled AR flue gas	c	Carbon
\dot{V}_{Air}	Volume flow of fresh air	eff	Effective
w_i	Mass fraction of species i	gas	Gas
x_i	Mole fraction of species i	Feed	Feedstock
X_i	Conversion of species i	FR	Fuel Reactor
		fine	Fine fraction
		in	Inlet
		o	Oxygen
		OC	Oxygen Carrier
		out	Outlet
		ox	Oxidized
		red	Reduced
		RL	Refractory Lining
		s	Solid
		tot	Total
		th	Thermal
<i>Greek Symbols</i>			
ΔX_s	Difference in oxidation degree of OC		
ΔH_R	Reaction enthalpy		
λ	Air-to-fuel equivalence ratio		
η_{CGE}	Cold gas efficiency		
ϕ_λ	Ratio of effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratios for FR and AR		
τ_s	Solids residence time		

or fluidized bed reactors (Huseyin et al., 2014; Condori et al., 2021a; Condori et al., 2021b), using oxygen carriers of different nature (Huang et al., Jan. 2014; Hildor et al., 2020; Moldenhauer et al., 2018; He et al., 2011; Zhao et al., 2015; Abdalazeez et al., 2022). Moreover, the suitability of various biomass-based feedstocks, such as rice husks (Ge et al., 2016a; Abdalazeez et al., 2022; Ge et al., 2016b), rice straw (Hu et al., Feb. 2019), sawdust (Xu et al., Nov. 2021; He et al., 2011), and wood pellets (Condori et al., 2021b; Hildor et al., 2020; Moldenhauer et al., 2018) has been established for CLG operation. In their review, Goel

et al. (2022) present a comprehensive overview over those endeavors, highlighting the most important variables affecting the efficiency of the CLG system, such as FR temperature, gasification agent, or properties of the utilized OC. More recent advances, conducted in larger pilot plants, aim towards the large-scale implementation of the CLG technology (Ge et al., 2016a; Pissot et al., 2018; Condori et al., 2022), thus tackling fundamental questions with regard to process stability, operability, and efficiency.

One aspect that has been found to be crucial for up-scaling of the CLG

Fig. 1. Illustration of CLG process.

Fig. 2. Simplified process flow diagram of the 1 MW_{th} CLG pilot plant.

technology is related to the dual-purpose of the OC material, circulating between AR and FR (Dieringer et al., 2020; Samprón et al., 2021). As it does not only transport O₂ from the air reactor (AR) to the fuel reactor (FR), but is also responsible for the transport of sensible heat between the two reactors (Ohlemüller et al., 2016; Pröll et al., 2010), it allows for a N₂-free oxidation of the feedstock inside the FR and facilitates a stabilization of FR temperatures at the desired levels (i.e. >800 °C). In contrast to chemical looping combustion, partial oxidation of the feedstock is desired inside the FR in CLG (Huseyin et al., 2014; Ge et al., 2016b). This means that the oxygen availability in the FR has to be limited, while large heat fluxes to the FR are required, in order to maintain a stable fuel reactor temperature despite the pronounced occurrence of endothermic gasification reactions (Dieringer et al., 2020; Samprón et al., 2021). Therefore, novel process control strategies and plant designs, allowing for a de-coupling of oxygen and heat transport between the AR and FR are required in CLG (Dieringer et al., 2020; Samprón et al., 2021). In theory, a number of process control concepts are viable to achieve autothermal (i.e. without external heating) CLG operation. Yet, modeling approaches (Dieringer et al., 2020; Samprón et al., 2021) as well as initial test runs in small (Condori et al., 2021a,b) and medium-sized pilots (Condori et al., 2022) showed that restricting the air supply in the AR to reduce the overall air-to-fuel ratio to values below unity, hence obtaining gasification conditions, is the most promising approach. Therefore, the 1 MW_{th} pilot plant located at the Technical University Darmstadt, was adapted accordingly, to allow for autothermal CLG operation in an industrially relevant environment.

The aim of this study was to demonstrate that the production of a high-grade synthesis gas is feasible via autothermal CLG, using the adapted 1 MW_{th} pilot plant in combination with a tailored novel process control concept. The presented work comprises overarching results of the first-ever successful autothermal CLG operation, including a comprehensive set of live-data for the most important system variables, as well as characterization of OC samples collected throughout the continuous 14 days of operation. On the basis of these data-sets, a wholistic acting mechanism for the CLG technology is proposed, laying the ground-work for the systemic understanding of an industrially operated chemical looping gasifier. Moreover, the presented results show that using the suggested process control strategy allows for the

production of a high-calorific syngas in semi-industrial scale, underlining the competitiveness of the CLG technology.

2. Experimental

2.1. 1 MW_{th} pilot plant layout

The layout of the 1 MW_{th} CLG pilot plant is described in detail elsewhere (Marx et al., 2021). Therefore, only the main features of the pilot, schematically shown in Fig. 2, are elaborated hereinafter.

The reactor system, consisting of an air reactor (0.59 m inner diameter, 8.66 m height), a fuel reactor (0.4 m inner diameter, 11.35 m height), and three coupling elements (two loop seals and a J-valve), is refractory lined to minimize heat losses, allowing for autothermal operation (i.e. without electrical heating). Both reactors are designed as circulating fluidized bed (CFB) reactors and are equipped with water-cooled ash sluicing screws for continuous or batch-wise material extraction from the bed. Moreover, each reactor can be additionally heated with propane, using a start-up burner or a bed lance. The AR has a design temperature of 1050 °C and can be fluidized with air or a mixture of air and recycled AR flue gas, which can be electrically pre-heated to temperatures up to 375 °C. For process control reasons, the inlet gas composition (O₂, CO₂) is measured for the AR (see Section 2.3.2).¹ The fuel reactor has a design temperature of 970 °C and can be fluidized with air, steam, a mixture of steam and CO₂, or a mixture of air and CO₂. The fluidization media can be electrically pre-heated to temperatures up to 450 °C. Each reactor is equipped with a cyclone for gas solid separation and a loop seal to prevent bypassing of gasses. Global solid circulation between the two reactors is achieved with a J-valve, connecting the loop seal (LS) of the AR (LS4.1) with the fuel reactor. The circulating mass flow between both reactors can be adjusted by changing the fluidization flow of the J-Valve, which can be fluidized with nitrogen or CO₂. For the fuel reactor, all entrained material leaving the

¹ CO₂ is measured inside the AR primary air line as CO₂ formed inside the AR through the combustion of residual char coming from the FR can be recycled back to the primary air line when AR flue gas recirculation is initiated.

Fig. 3. Illustration of CLG control concept utilized in 1 MW_{th} pilot plant.

riser is directly transferred into the AR via LS4.5, which is fluidized with nitrogen or CO₂. On the other hand, the option of internal solid circulation via LS4.1, fluidized with nitrogen,² exists for the AR. This internal solid circulation stabilizes the hydrodynamics of the overall system. A solid fuel flow up to 250 kg/h corresponding to a thermal power of about 1.24 MW is introduced into the dense bed of the FR via an oil-cooled feeding screw. Fuel supply is either achieved from a fuel silo or via big bags through a weighted container equipped with a dosing screw, allowing for an exact control of the fuel mass flow. The fuel reactor off-gasses first pass a syngas cooler, where it is cooled to a temperature of approx. 350 °C. Subsequently, the gas composition (CO, CO₂, O₂, H₂, CH₄) is measured online. To allow for safe venting to the environment, the FR product gas is then transferred through a hot gas filter, operated at up to 250 °C, using a hot syngas compressor, before it enters a thermal oxidizer, required for full conversion of all hydrocarbon species to CO₂ and H₂O. After online gas sampling (CO, CO₂, O₂, SO₂, NO), the off-gasses from the AR are cooled in a heat exchanger, to a temperature <250 °C. Thereafter, the gas enters a fabric filter for dedusting. Downstream of the induced draft fan controlling the freeboard pressure of the AR (see PIC2 in Fig. 3), the AR flue gasses can be vented to the environment through a stack or can be partly recycled back to the AR airbox via the primary-air fan. In order to maintain constant reactor inventories throughout operation, the pilot is equipped with a pneumatically fed, make-up feeding system, allowing for the controlled introduction of up to 200 kg/h of the OC ilmenite into the standpipe of LS4.1.

2.2. Materials

2.2.1. OC bed material - ilmenite

Ilmenite from the Norwegian Company Titania AS, which was successfully deployed during previous chemical looping experiments in the 1 MW_{th} pilot (Ohlemüller et al., 2016; Ströhle et al., 2015; Ohlemüller et al., 2017), was used as OC for the CLG experiments presented in this study. For the fresh material, a bulk density of 2550 kg/m³, a particle density of 4486 kg/m³, and a mean particle diameter of 111 μm ($d_{p,10} = 31 \mu\text{m}$, $d_{p,90} = 224 \mu\text{m}$) was determined.

2.2.2. Feedstock

The feedstock used for pilot testing are industrial wood pellets conforming to the Norm ENplus A1, purchased from Eckard GmbH, Germany.

² Fluidization with air is also possible for LS4.1, however this option is neglected due to safety reasons (risk of air bypassing to FR).

Table 1

Proximate and Ultimate analysis for industrial wood pellets.

Component	wt.-% (d.a.f.)	Component	wt.-% (a.r.)
C	50.8	C-fix	13.3
H	6	Volatiles	79.6
O	43.2	Ash	0.65
N	0.07	Moisture	6.5
S	0.008		
Cl	0.006		

The pellets exhibit a cylindrical shape ($l \sim 10\text{--}25 \text{ mm}$, $d \sim 6 \text{ mm}$), a bulk density of 650 kg/m³, and a lower heating value of 17.96 MJ/kg. Proximate and Ultimate analysis for the pellets are given in Table 1.

2.3. Process control concept

2.3.1. Process control alternatives

Previous studies concluded that restricting the air supply in the AR, thus lowering the air-to-fuel equivalence ratio (λ) of the entire process below unity, is the most auspicious approach to obtain gasification conditions in chemical looping (Dieringer et al., 2020; Samprón et al., 2021). Yet, as the air supplied in the AR is not only responsible for providing the oxygen driving the chemical looping process, but is also crucial for obtaining sufficient solid circulation between the two reactors (Dieringer et al., 2020; Samprón et al., 2021), there are three conceivable options to achieve the desired gas velocity in the AR ($u_{0,AR}$) and the reduction in λ simultaneously:

- Designing the AR specifically for CLG operation (i.e. with a smaller inner diameter than for CLC operation) to reduce the amount of fluidization medium required.
- Recycling AR flue gasses to the AR air box and mixing it with the inlet air.
- Diluting the inlet air to the AR with an inert (e.g. N₂).

The last option signifies a straight-forward as well as easy to implement and validated (Condori et al., 2021a,b, 2022) option, however leads to significant operational costs due to the constant consumption of inerts. Hence, this option should be neglected for units of substantial thermal load (>50–100 kW_{th}). The second option leads to starkly reduced operational costs, when compared to (iii), yet comes with additional process complexity, requiring additional measurement and control (MSR) equipment for process control. Moreover, the recycled AR flue gas leads to increased compression demands for the AR primary-air fan and has to be brought to reactor temperatures, requiring additional heat. In contrast, the first approach allows for a direct process control in CLG without additional operational costs for inerts and pre-heating of recycled AR flue gas or equipment requirements, owing to its direct tailoring to the required process conditions. However, it is clear that this approach is only viable for greenfield plants, as variations in reactor dimensions are not easily attainable for existing units. Moreover, when using this approach, the plant layout does not allow for meaningful variations in λ (e.g. in case of significant changes in the composition of the supplied feedstock, requiring more or less heat supply in the gasifier), as λ and $u_{0,AR}$ are directly coupled. Therefore, the plant flexibility is reduced.

Based on this brief evaluation, it becomes obvious that only the second option, i.e. the extension of the existing 1 MW_{th} pilot plant with an AR flue gas recirculation line, signifies a viable option for its adaption for chemical looping gasification, allowing for meaningful parameter variations. On top of this, the suggested process control concept could

also be considered for a full-scale CLG setup, in which feedstock of varying quality, source, or nature is to be converted, necessitating operation at varying λ to fulfill the heat balance. The implementation of this concept is described in detail in the subsequent chapter.

2.3.2. Implementation of process control concept

For the independent control of two parameters, the AR gas velocity $u_{O,AR}$ and the air-to-fuel equivalence ratio λ , two separate control loops are necessary. The process control concept described below, relying on three independent control loops, is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Firstly, the gas velocity in the AR is controlled indirectly via the total inlet volume flow into the AR (FY1 from FYC1). The volume flow is measured with an aperture measurement, consisting of an orifice plate, a pressure measurement (PI1), a differential pressure measurement (PDI2), and a temperature measurement (TI1) inside the primary-air line of the AR. The calculated value for the inlet volume flow is then controlled through a speed controller (SIC1), controlling the rotary speed of the primary-air fan via a frequency converter. This control loop thus allows for an independent control of $u_{O,AR}$ via the total volume flow by the operator through either setting a fixed rotational speed for the primary-air fan or selecting the desired volume flow for the controller (FYC1). In order to control the oxygen input into the reactor and hence the air-to-fuel equivalence ratio λ of the CLG process, the primary-air line is equipped with an online oxygen measurement (QI1 from QIC1). To determine the oxygen input, the oxygen concentration (QI1 from QIC1) is multiplied with the volume flow entering the AR (FY1). With this knowledge, the oxygen input can then be controlled via a regulating flap in the AR flue gas recycle, which is opened automatically by a dedicated controller (QIC1) to increase the flue gas recycle, thus decreasing the air input and vice versa. Consequently, the operator can set a desired oxygen input and hence a fixed value for λ by either selecting the desired oxygen concentration inside the primary-air line or by manually positioning the regulating flap to a designated position. In theory, these two control loops are sufficient for the desired purpose. However, to further increase system stability, a third control loop was implemented. This control loop regulates the pressure upstream of the primary-air fan through a second gas flap located inside the air intake line. Here, the pressure controller (PIC1) opens the regulating flap to reduce the pressure and closes it to increase the pressure. By setting a fixed value for the pressure upstream of the primary-air fan, it is guaranteed that the primary-air fan runs at a constant rotational speed for a given volume flow even when the AR flue gas recirculation is adjusted to control the air-to-fuel equivalence ratio of the process.

2.4. Operating conditions

In March and April 2022, several periods of stable multi-hour CLG operation were obtained within a two-week test campaign, during which the 1 MW_{th} pilot unit was continuously operated 24 h/day. In total, the pilot was operated for ~100 h in chemical looping mode during this period. To allow for meaningful comparisons and illustrations of important trends, thirty Operating periods (BP) were selected for analysis, during each of which the most important boundary conditions, summarized in Table 4 in the appendix, were kept constant. All thirty Operating periods were split into 20-minutes sub-periods, yielding a total of 177 sub-periods for subsequent analysis, which also facilitates the investigation of potential changes occurring within the individual operating points. Moreover, three transient periods (denoted as TP-1, TP-2, and TP-3) with a duration of approx. 5–8 hours, leading up to stable CLG operation, are described in detail in this paper. These transient periods are characterized by a transient sub-period induced through a targeted adaption of the AR recycling ratio by the operator, entailing a characteristic switch towards gasification conditions. The boundary conditions for these periods are given in Table 5 in the appendix.

2.5. Evaluation parameters

To evaluate the merit of the novel CLG control concept, several evaluation parameters are introduced. Firstly, the air-to-fuel equivalence ratio, given by the ratio between the available oxygen for solid feedstock conversion and the oxygen required for full feedstock combustion, is used to quantify the oxygen input into the gasifier system. Here, the numerator constitutes the difference of the oxygen fed to the AR, $\dot{m}_{O,AR,in}$, and the amount of oxygen required for combustion of the additional propane fed to the AR via the propane lance:

$$\lambda = \frac{\dot{m}_{O,AR,in} - \dot{m}_{C_3H_8,AR} \cdot R_{C_3H_8}}{\dot{m}_{Feed} \cdot R_{Feed}} \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), $R_{C_3H_8}$ (3.628 kg_O/kg) and R_{Feed} (1.306 kg_O/kg) signify the oxygen demand for full conversion of propane and the biomass feedstock, estimated from the elemental composition, respectively. According to this definition, (close to) full combustion of the feedstock is attained for air-to-fuel equivalence ratios larger than unity ($\lambda > 1$), while gasification processes require sub-stoichiometric oxygen feeding (i.e. $\lambda < 1$). However, it has to be noted that in chemical looping processes incomplete feedstock conversion is generally obtained for $\lambda \geq 1$ (Adánez et al., 2006; Pérez-Vega et al., 2016; Ohlemüller, 2019), as the oxidation of volatiles by the OC in the FR is limited by kinetics (Fossdal et al., May 2011; Liu et al., Oct. 2013) as well as gas/solid mixing.

As for some Operating periods, not all oxygen fed to the AR is consumed in it, the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio, considering the difference between the input and output of elemental oxygen for the AR ($\dot{m}_{O,AR,in}$, $\dot{m}_{O,AR,out}$), is a useful tool to evaluate how much oxygen is taken up by the OC inside the AR (Condori et al., 2022):³

$$\lambda_{AR,eff} = \frac{\dot{m}_{O,AR,in} - \dot{m}_{O,AR,out}}{\dot{m}_{Feed} \cdot R_{Feed}} \quad (2)$$

Similarly, the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio in the FR can be calculated considering the input and output of elemental oxygen for the FR, thereby constituting how much oxygen is released inside the FR by the OC (Condori et al., 2022):

$$\lambda_{FR,eff} = \frac{\dot{m}_{O,FR,out} - \dot{m}_{O,FR,in}}{\dot{m}_{Feed} \cdot R_{Feed}} \quad (3)$$

Clearly, the system is in steady state if $\lambda_{AR,eff} = \lambda_{FR,eff}$, which means that the OC takes up and releases the same amount of oxygen in the AR and FR, respectively. Hence, the quotient of the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratios of the AR and FR (ϕ_λ) can be utilized to evaluate the state of the CLG unit (Condori et al., 2022):

$$\phi_\lambda = \frac{\lambda_{FR,eff}}{\lambda_{AR,eff}} \begin{cases} < 1 & \text{Oxygen accumulation in OC} \\ = 1 & \text{System in steady state} \\ > 1 & \text{Oxygen depletion from OC} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

As described in Section 2.3.2, λ is controlled through a recycling of AR flue gasses for AR fluidization. To quantify the extent of recirculation, the AR flue gas recycling ratio is introduced:

$$RR_{AR} = \frac{\dot{V}_{Rec,AR}}{\dot{V}_{Rec,AR} + \dot{V}_{Air,AR}} \quad (5)$$

Here $RR_{AR}=0$ signifies operation with pure air, while $RR_{AR}=1$ signifies operation with pure AR flue gas. The recirculation rate can easily be calculated by a mass balance around the primary-air line (more details, see derivation in Chapter A.1 in the appendix):

$$RR_{AR} = \frac{x_{O_2,AR,in} - 21 \text{ vol.}\%}{x_{O_2,AR,out} - 21 \text{ vol.}\%} = \frac{x_{CO_2,AR,in}}{x_{CO_2,AR,out}} \quad (6)$$

³ In Eq. (1), (2) and (3), the oxygen inlet and outlet into the AR/FR are evaluated by using the respective volume flow measurements (venturi nozzles and orifice plates) and online gas analyzers (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 4. a) Illustration of reactor system with indication of solid sampling points. b) Schematical detail view of solid sampling setup.

$$X_{C,AR} = \frac{\dot{m}_{gas,AR} \cdot \left(\frac{w_{CO,AR}}{M_{CO}} + \frac{w_{CO_2,AR}}{M_{CO_2}} \right) \cdot M_C - \dot{m}_{C_{3H_8,AR}} \cdot w_{C,C_{3H_8,AR}} - \frac{x_{CO_2,AR,in}}{M_{CO_2}} \cdot (\dot{m}_{Rec,AR} + \dot{m}_{Air,AR}) \cdot M_C}{\dot{m}_{Feed} \cdot w_{C,Feed}} \quad (9)$$

In order to simplify the subsequent considerations, the cold gas efficiency (CGE), η_{CGE} , relating the energy content of the produced syngas at the FR outlet to the energy input through the solid feedstock (Higman and van der Burgt, 2008; De et al., 2018), is used to describe the efficiency of the gasification processes:

$$\eta_{CGE} = \frac{\dot{n}_{gas,FR,out} \cdot (x_{CH_4,FR,out} \cdot LHV_{CH_4} + x_{CO,FR,out} \cdot LHV_{CO,FR} + x_{H_2,FR,out} \cdot LHV_{H_2})}{\dot{m}_{Feed} \cdot LHV_{Feed} + \dot{m}_{C_{3H_8,AR}} \cdot LHV_{C_{3H_8}} - \dot{Q}_{cool,AR}} \quad (7)$$

Here the propane input ($P_{th,C_{3H_8}} = \dot{m}_{C_{3H_8,AR}} \cdot LHV_{C_{3H_8}}$) and the cooling duty ($\dot{Q}_{cool,AR}$) of the AR cooling lances⁴ are considered, to obtain a meaningful value.

Another important parameter for the CLG unit is the amount of carbon converted in the FR, which is given by:

$$X_{C,FR} = \frac{\dot{n}_{gas,FR,out} \cdot \left(x_{CH_4,FR,out} \cdot \frac{M_C}{M_{CH_4}} + x_{CO,FR,out} \cdot \frac{M_C}{M_{CO}} + x_{CO_2,FR,out} \cdot \frac{M_C}{M_{CO_2}} \right) \cdot M_C}{\dot{m}_{Feed} \cdot w_{C,Feed}} \quad (8)$$

Char travelling to the AR together with the circulating solid is converted to CO₂ there. In case of $\lambda \ll 1$, CO can also be formed in minor amounts inside the AR, so that the carbon conversion inside the AR is given by:

⁴ Generally, cooling in the AR is not desired during CLG operation. However, due to constructional reasons, the cooling lances of the AR in the 1 MW_{th} unit cannot be fully extracted from the reactor and hence lead to heat extraction during operation.

The total carbon conversion inside the CLG unit is the sum of the AR and FR char conversion and should be close to 1, as the only way for carbon to “escape” the unit is in particulate form towards the FR or AR filter.

$$X_{C,tot} = X_{C,FR} + X_{C,AR} \leq 1 \quad (10)$$

2.6. Solid sampling and analysis

A detailed elaboration of the sampling and analysis procedure of the OC samples is presented by Marx et al. (2023). To further expand analysis, this methodology is also applied in this study. Here, solid samples were taken from the standpipe of the two loop seals during CLG operation (see Fig. 4a), using a dedicated sampling setup illustrated in Fig. 4b. In order to ensure samples representing the current process state, the sampling tube was flushed with nitrogen to remove all material in the sampling tube and replace it with fresh material. The process was observed via infra-red thermometer and was deemed successful when temperatures 300 °C on the outside were reached, signifying that “fresh”, hot material had entered the sampling line. The sample (300–700 g) was then discharged from the loop seal via ball valves into a sealed vessel where it was left for cool down for approx. two hours in order to prevent reaction with ambient air. Afterwards the sample was removed from the system.

For analysis of the carbon content, the samples were first classified into two particle fractions using a 400 μm sieve. The coarse fraction (containing the majority of the transported char) was not considered further, as due to the particle size of the raw material (see Chapter 2.2.1) it can be assumed that ilmenite particles are not present inside the coarse fraction. The fine fraction was processed in a commercially available elemental analysis system (Elementar vario MACRO cube in CHNS

Fig. 5. Progression of important process and evaluation parameters over time for TP-1.

From top to bottom: a.) FR and b.) AR temperature, c.) cold gas efficiency (η_{CGE}), d.) H_2/CO -ratio in FR product gas, e.) oxygen concentration at AR outlet ($x_{O_2,AR,out}$), f.) air-to-fuel equivalence ratio (λ), g.) oxygen concentration at AR inlet ($x_{O_2,AR,in}$), h.) AR gas velocity, and i.) AR flue gas recycling ratio (RR_{AR}), calculated from O_2 (-) and CO_2 (:) balance. Arrows with diamonds at the end signify the sampling time of a given solid sample.

setup). Each fraction was analyzed in triplicate with a sample mass of 50 mg, using a method providing oxygen according to the approximate carbon content and oxygen uptake. To determine the oxidation degree (X_s) of the samples, their weight change in an oxidizing atmosphere was subsequently determined by oxidizing a sample mass of approx. 5 g in a laboratory oven at 900 °C with the mass being determined before ($m_{LS,1}$) and after ($m_{LS,2}$) oxidation.

In chemical looping, the oxidation degree of the OC is generally given by Adanez et al. (2012); Larsson et al. (2014):

$$X_{s,i} = \frac{m_{OC,i} - m_{OC,red}}{R_{OC} \cdot m_{OC,ox}} \quad (11)$$

Here, $m_{OC,red}$ and $m_{OC,ox}$ are the mass of an OC sample in a fully reduced and oxidized state respectively, while $m_{OC,i}$ is the mass of the OC sample in its current state. Using the mass of loop seal samples before and after oxidation and assuming that the latter signifies a fully oxidized OC sample (i.e. $m_{OC,ox} = m_{LS,2}$), one can thus calculate the oxidation degree:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{s,i} &= \frac{m_{LS,1} \cdot (1 - w_{C,LS,fine}) - m_{LS,2} \cdot (1 - R_{OC})}{R_{OC} \cdot m_{LS,2}} \\ &= 1 - \frac{m_{LS,2} - m_{LS,1} \cdot (1 - w_{C,LS,fine})}{R_{OC} \cdot m_{LS,2}} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

To arrive at Eq. (12), the following assumptions are used:

i The extent to which the OC sample can be reduced is given by the oxygen transport capacity (R_{OC}). For the utilized ilmenite, an oxygen transport capacity of 3.7 wt.-% was determined (Condori et al., 2021b). This value falls slightly below the theoretical oxygen transport capacity for the redox couple $Fe_2TiO_5/FeTiO_3$ (Adanez et al., 2012). With the given value of R_{OC} the samples' reduced mass can be calculated by:

$$m_{OC,red} = m_{OC,ox} \cdot (1 - R_{OC}) = m_{LS,2} \cdot (1 - R_{OC}) \quad (13)$$

ii Since the fresh loop seal sample contains small fraction of char, originating from the carbon slip occurring between AR and FR (Huseyin et al., 2014; Markström et al., 2013; Cuadrat et al., 2012), the carbon content of the LS samples has to be considered for the calculation of the oxidation degree. As the char can be assumed to be fully burned-off inside the laboratory oven, the "real" loop seal mass ($m_{OC,i}$), can be calculated by:

$$m_{OC,i} = m_{LS,1} - m_{c,fine} = m_{LS,1} \cdot (1 - w_{C,LS,fine}) \quad (14)$$

iii Due to the low content of ash for the raw feedstock (see Table 1), it can be assumed that the ash content inside the LS samples is negligible.

Fig. 6. Progression OC oxidation degree when increasing the air reactor recycling ratio (RR_{AR}). The reduction extent at the FR outlet is determined by FR reaction kinetics and the FR residence time. a) Minor decrease in oxidation degree at FR outlet ($X_{s,FR}$), b) Significant decrease in oxidation degree at FR outlet. Adapted from Dieringer et al. (2020).

3. Results and discussion

During application of the novel process control concept in the 1 MW_{th} scale, it was observed that the CLG unit displays a characteristic transient system response to changes in the AR recycling ratio, giving meaningful insights into the mechanics of the CLG process. This behavior is explained on the basis of three different transient periods in Chapter 3.1. Subsequently, Chapter 3.2 illustrates how the new process control concept affects process efficiency in steady-state.

3.1. Transient system response to application of novel process control concept

3.1.1. System response of 1 MW_{th} CLG unit during transient periods

The progression of the most important process parameters for the first transient period under consideration (TP-1) is illustrated in Fig. 5. It includes three distinct sub-periods on April 10th, 2022. Between 6:00 and approx. 8:00 h, the pilot plant was operated in steady state without AR flue gas recirculation (TP-1a). Thereafter, operators started AR flue gas recirculation at approx. 8:00 h, initiating the transient sub-period of the process stretching until approx. 12:00 h (TP-1b). During this sub-period, minor adaptations with regard to the AR flue gas recycling were carried out by the operator to reach the destined operating period. Between 12:00 h and 14:00 h the process reached steady state and did not show any major variations in the operating and evaluation parameters (TP-1c).

When considering Fig. 5, the interventions by the operator are best visible in the AR recycling ratio (Fig. 5i). By repositioning the flue gas recirculation flap, the recirculation rate of the process was sharply increased from 0 to 0.15 at 8:00 h.⁵ As a consequence, the inlet oxygen concentration to the AR decreased from 21 to 16.9 vol.-% (see Fig. 5g). Due to the process control concept, described in detail in Section 2.3.2, the gas velocity $u_{0,AR}$ was maintained at a constant value of 3.3–3.4 m/s (see Fig. 5h), leading to stable hydrodynamics for the CLG process throughout the entire transient period under consideration.⁶ However, as the air-input into the system was reduced, while the thermal load of the gasifier was kept constant throughout the entire transient period, the air-to-fuel equivalence ratio dropped from a value of 0.65 to 0.49 (see Fig. 5f).

⁵ Minor operator adaptations at later stages lead to an increase of this value to 0.19 over the considered period.

⁶ Apart from $u_{0,AR} = \text{const.}$, this requires a constant reactor inventory, a constant gas velocity in the FR ($u_{0,FR}$) and constant volume flows for both loop seals and the J-Valve, which was the case here.

The first notable observation which can be made is that due to this decrease in λ , the oxygen concentration at the AR outlet immediately dropped to a value of 0 vol.-% (see Fig. 5e), meaning that all oxygen is consumed inside the AR. This means that the inlet oxygen is fully required for the re-oxidation of the OC, the combustion of the propane input into the AR and the combustion of char coming from the FR, denoted as carbon slip (Huseyin et al., 2014; Markström et al., 2013; Cuadrat et al., 2012). As the oxygen concentration remains at 0 vol.-% after this change in recirculation rate, it can be postulated that the OC is not fully oxidized inside the AR, as the oxygen availability is reduced. Yet, the oxygen release inside the FR is not altered instantly (see below), as the boundary conditions in the FR are not altered directly. Consequently, it can be assumed that the oxidation degree of the OC (X_s), given by the Eq. (11), is periodically decreased during each cycle, as postulated in a previous study (Dieringer et al., 2020), until new steady-state conditions are found.

To cast further light on this behavior, the theoretical progression of the oxidation degree of the oxygen carrier is illustrated in

Fig. 6. Clearly, not only the oxidation degree at the AR outlet, but also the change in oxidation degree between FR and AR (ΔX_s , see Eq. (15)) has to decrease for the new steady-state conditions (see Fig. 6, $\Delta X_{s,1} > \Delta X_{s,2}$), as the OC circulation rate between the FR and AR is kept constant, yet less oxygen is being transported from the AR to the FR, due to the decrease in air input (Samprón et al., 2021):

$$\Delta X_s = X_{s,AR} - X_{s,FR} = \frac{m_{OC,AR} - m_{OC,FR}}{R_{OC} \cdot m_{OC,ox}} \quad (15)$$

Depending on the interplay of the kinetics of the different occurring reactions and the OC residence time in the FR, determining to which extent the OC is reduced in the FR (Liu et al., Oct. 2013), the oxidation degree at the outlet of the AR and FR can either decrease slightly (see Fig. 6a) or sharply (see Fig. 6b) until steady state conditions are attained.⁷

The above elucidations on the ensuing shift in the oxidation degree of the OC are supported, when considering the progression of the H₂/CO ratio (see Fig. 5d), and the cold gas efficiency (see Fig. 5c), over time. Clearly, the hydrogen to carbon monoxide ratio in the FR product gas increases continuously after the increase in the AR recycling ratio during sub-period TP-1b. This can be explained by the fact, that due to its more favorable reaction kinetics when compared to CO, hydrogen is preferentially oxidized on the oxygen carrier (Abad et al., 2011). As less oxygen is available from the OC with decreasing $X_{s,AR}$, oxidation of syngas

⁷ For long residence times and high FR temperatures values close to zero can also be obtained for $X_{s,FR}$ (Condori et al., Feb. 2021).

Fig. 7. Progression of effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio of FR (b) and AR (c) and their ratio (a) over time for TP-3. The red shaded area in (c) denotes steady state conditions with $\phi_\lambda = 1 \pm 0.05$.

Table 2

Oxidation degree (X_S) in% for OC samples collected from LS4.1 and LS4.5 during the transient periods TP-1, TP-2, and TP-3. Sampling times for each sample are indicated in Fig. 5 (TP-1), Fig. 17 (TP-2), and Fig. 18 (TP-3) and are listed in Table 3 in the Appendix.

Period	TP-1		TP-2		TP-3	
Loop Seal	LS4.1	LS4.5	LS4.1	LS4.5	LS4.1	LS4.5
Sub-Period	TP-1a		TP-2b		-	
Sample-#	S-42	S-43	S-60	S-59	-	-
X_S [%]	94.6 ± 0.1	74.7 ± 0.5	81.2 ± 0.3	60.9 ± 0.2	-	-
ΔX_S [%]	19.9 ± 0.3		20.4 ± 0.2		-	-
Sub-Period	-		TP-2c		TP-3c	
Sample-#	-	-	S-61	S-62	S-66	S-65
X_S [%]	-	-	81.8 ± 0.1	65.8 ± 0.4	83.7 ± 1.1	64.4 ± 0.6
ΔX_S [%]	-	-	16.0 ± 0.3		19.3 ± 0.8	

species on the oxygen carrier occurs less pronouncedly and as hydrogen was previously oxidized to greater extents, the H_2/CO ratio increases from 0.94 to 1.47.⁸ Following the same logic, the cold gas efficiency of the process steadily increases from a value of 0.20 to 0.27, as less oxygen is released by the OC inside the FR and hence more chemical energy is maintained in the FR product gases. Yet, in contrast to the other variables previously discussed, the change in H_2/CO -ratio and the cold gas efficiency does not occur instantly, but over a duration of approx. four hours. Firstly, this system inertia can be explained by the fact that each OC particle has to gradually reach new steady-state conditions (e.g. getting reduced from $X_{S,FR,1}$ to $X_{S,FR,2}$). Secondly, it can be explained by the fact that in order to reach steady-state conditions, the entire reactor inventory, (800–1000 kg), has to be reduced to lower oxidation degrees until equilibrium is reached. Thus, this chemical inertia of the system has to be considered, when adapting process variables affecting the air-to-fuel equivalence ratio of the process.

When considering the reactor temperatures measured during the transient period TP-1 (see Fig. 5a & Fig. 5b), it becomes visible, that all reactor temperatures decrease as soon as the AR flue gas recirculation is switched on, with average AR temperatures dropping from 991 to 942 °C, while FR temperatures decrease from 874 to 835 °C over the duration of the transient period. This can be explained by the fact, that less oxidizing reactions occur and hence reaction exothermicity decreases. Similar to the H_2/CO ratio and the cold gas efficiency, reactor temperatures require approx. four hours to reach stable values. Again, this can be explained by the fact that as the oxygen release from the OC inside the

FR is diminished during sub-period TP-1b, the total reaction exothermicity decreases. Consequently, the heat release from the CLG unit decreases and system temperatures drop along with the decrease in oxygen transport from the AR to the FR. Moreover, this finding suggests that the transient behavior of the reactor system might in part also be related to the refractory lining of the reactor system, slowly reacting to the changes occurring inside the reactor and hence cushioning a rapid drop in reactor temperatures. As reactor temperatures are also dependent on the temperature of the refractory lining, with the temperature gradient between gas phase and refractory wall determining the heat flux to the surroundings, this means that there exists a feedback loop between the reactor temperature, determined by the chemical reactions occurring inside the reactor system, and the refractory lining temperature. Therefore, larger CLG units, for which the surface-to-volume ratio is much smaller than for the 1 MW_{th} unit, might show a more rapid system response than what has been observed here, depending on which effect is the more dominant (i.e. the slow reduction of the OC or the thermal inertia of the refractory lining). Another important finding that can be derived from the temperature profiles shown in Fig. 5a and Fig. 5b is that the temperature difference between both reactors stays constant during the entire transient period, starting at a value of 117 K and ending at a 107 K. This again shows that throughout the entire period, solid circulation was maintained constant, underlining the effectivity of the novel process control concept.

A similar behavior was observed for all parameters and variables highlighted above for the other two transient periods under consideration (TP-2 & TP-3), meaning that the observed behavior occurs in a comparable fashion, when the AR flue gas recirculation is initiated (see Chapter A.2 in the appendix). This means that although slight differences in terms of the transient switch-over times or the extent to which the evaluation parameters change are visible, the governing phenomena

⁸ Another reason for this could be the decrease in FR temperature, going in hand with the increase in RR_{AR} , which leads to shift in the WGS equilibrium and a decrease in char conversion.

Fig. 8. Effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio in the AR as a function of the flue gas recycling ratio in the AR for different thermal loads of propane firing for all operating periods given in Table 4.

for the observed behavior are the same.

3.1.2. Oxygen balancing during transient periods

As mentioned before, it is postulated that by reducing the oxygen input into the AR through initiating AR flue gas recycling, the extent to which the OC is oxidized inside the AR reduces with each cycle (see Fig. 6). If this is the case, it should also be visible in the oxygen balance of the CLG system, as the oxygen carrier should be depleted of oxygen during the transient period (i.e. $\phi_\lambda > 1$, see Eq. (4)). Fig. 7 shows that the expected behavior was observed during the transient periods, showing the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratios as well as their quotient for the period TP-3. Fig. 7c shows that as soon as the recycling ratio is started by the operator at 11:00 on 12th April 2022, initiating the transient sub-period TP-3b, the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio in the AR immediately drops from a value of 0.45 to a value of 0.38. This indicates that less oxygen is taken up by the OC inside the AR instantly, due to the limitation in oxygen availability. On the other hand, the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio inside the FR declines slowly over the entire duration of TP-3b (see Fig. 7b). For one, this shows that the OC releases less and less oxygen inside the FR until a new steady-state is obtained, indicating that its oxygen release inside the FR is slowly restricted and the control concept yields the desired results. When considering the transient response, Fig. 7b suggests that the lowered oxygen release inside the FR results from gradual changes taking place within the OC throughout the entire transient period. Again, this points to the fact that for each cycle the OC gets more reduced and hence its oxygen release kinetics decelerate inside the FR (Abad et al., 2011; Ohlemüller et al., 2018), leading to lower oxygen release rates. The ensuing oxygen depletion of the OC is visually highlighted in blue shading in Fig. 7a, showing that ϕ_λ increases to an elevated level throughout the entire transient sub-period TP-3b, indicating that oxygen is “consumed” by the occurring chemical reactions within the transient period, before it drops to its initial value as soon as steady state conditions are reached in sub-period TP-3c.⁹ Consequently, it can be

⁹ As visible from Eq. (4) oxygen depletion occurs for $\phi_\lambda > 1$. However, in Fig. 7c the baseline for oxygen depletion is set at a value of 1.15 for which ϕ_λ stagnates for the steady-state conditions TP-3a and TP-3c. Although mass and component (C, H, O) balances could be closed with an accuracy of $\pm 5\%$ for all operating points under consideration, it is believed that this upwards skew in ϕ_λ in Fig. 7c by 15% in the data can be accredited to measurement inaccuracy (e.g. venturi/aperture flow measurements, moisture measurement).

summarized that the OC inventory of the CLG unit serves as an oxygen storage, slowly releasing oxygen until a new steady state is reached, thereby playing an important role in the transient system response.

3.1.3. Behavior of the oxygen carrier inventory during transient periods

To further cast light onto the system’s behavior during the transient periods, analyses of solid samples at the AR and FR outlet can be considered, in order to enhance process understanding. One important question is which oxidation degree is reached at the FR and AR outlet in steady state. Moreover, it remains open whether each particle requires multiple cycles to reach this steady state, or if the length of the transient period is primarily dominated by the size of the reactor inventory (i.e. individual particles reach steady state conditions within $< 1-2$ cycles, yet multiple hours are required for a unit of the considered size until all particles have been cycled through the system). To cast light onto this, the oxidation degree of samples taken from both loop seals at different stages of the transient period TP-1, TP-2, and TP-3 are listed in Table 2. As expected, the higher oxidation degrees (X_s) are obtained for LS4.1 prior to the onset of AR flue gas recirculation (e.g. TP-1a: S-42: $X_s = 94.6$

$\pm 0.1\%$ vs. TP-3c S-66: $X_s = 83.7 \pm 1.1$) which can again be explained by the fact that while close to full oxidation of the OC is achieved in the AR when sufficient amounts of oxygen are supplied (i.e. $RR_{AR}=0$), only partial oxidation of the OC is attained in an oxygen deficient AR atmosphere. Consequently, as illustrated in Fig. 6, AR flue gas recirculation leads to a general drop in X_s for the entire CLG system (i.e. for AR & FR). While this observation supports the general mechanics of the process control concept, it does not directly explain how its application leads to a higher CLG process efficiency (i.e. higher CGEs). As stated before, cold gas efficiencies correlate with the amount of oxygen released inside the FR, leading to more or less complete feedstock conversion. The oxygen released in the FR is the one transported to it via the OC from the AR given by:

$$\dot{m}_{O,AR \rightarrow FR} = \dot{m}_{OC} \cdot R_{OC} \cdot \Delta X_s \quad (16)$$

Hence, for a constant global solid circulation (\dot{m}_{OC}), which can be assumed here as the hydrodynamic boundary conditions were not altered within each transient period, the change in the oxidation degree between AR and FR (ΔX_s) should decrease when RR_{AR} is increased. Again, this is corroborated by the data listed in Table 2 (e.g. TP-2b: S-59/60: $\Delta X_s = 20.4 \pm 0.2\%$) vs. TP-2c S-61/62: $\Delta X_s = 16.0 \pm 0.3\%$). The observed decrease in ΔX_s thus means due to its incomplete oxidation in the AR, the OC is less “keen” to release oxygen inside the FR, leading to a lower overall oxygen transport to the FR and hence higher cold gas efficiencies. This observation is also supported by kinetic studies performed with ilmenite, showing that OC reaction kinetics generally decrease with decreasing oxidation degree (Abad et al., 2011; Ohlemüller et al., 2018). In summary, the mechanics of the suggested process control concept can thus also be verified on the basis of solid samples collected from both loop seals during operation. Here, it can be observed that while the restriction of oxygen supply in the AR leads to a direct drop in X_s , this drop then leads to a subsequent decrease in ΔX_s and hence oxygen transport due to kinetic reasons. Moreover, it can be seen that all values obtained for oxidation degrees of the solid samples from LS4.5 listed in Table 2 are larger than 50%. Therefore, it can be postulated that the oxygen release inside the FR is restricted kinetically, preventing a full reduction ($X_s=0\%$, i.e. bulk of particle in $FeTiO_3$ phase) of the OC inside the FR. In a 1.5 kW_{th} unit, exhibiting a dissimilar layout to the 1 MW_{th} unit (i.e. FR in bubbling regime), allowing for distinctly larger solid residence times inside the FR, oxidation degrees $0\% < X_s, FR < 20\%$ were determined for $\lambda < 0.3$ at temperatures between 820 and 940 °C (Condori et al., 2021b). This shows that in case of more favorable kinetics (higher FR temperatures) (Abad et al., 2011; Ohlemüller et al., 2018) and longer residence times (Liu et al., Oct. 2013), the OC is reduced to lower oxidation degrees inside the FR. Yet, even at these conditions, full reduction is not attained due to kinetic reasons. In case

Fig. 9. Outlet AR O₂ concentration as a function of the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio in the AR as a function of the flue gas recycling ratio in the AR for different oxygen concentrations at AR outlet for all operating periods given in Table 4. Gray arrows denote the progression of x_{O₂,AR,out} with increasing RR_{AR} (CLG) and P_{th,C₃H₈,AR} (DFBG), respectively.

this kinetic barrier is overcome (e.g. through higher FR temperatures) and the oxygen release inside the FR is restricted due to thermodynamic reasons (i.e. X_{s,FR}=0), the time required to reach steady state conditions after changes in RR_{AR} would decrease, as steady state conditions are reached inside the FR as soon as X_{s,FR}=0 is attained. Nonetheless, the system would still require a certain stabilization time for the entire OC inventory to reach its fully reduced state.

3.2. Steady-state system response to application of novel process control concept

While the investigation of the transient system response of the CLG unit to changes in the air supply provides insights into the underlying phenomena, comparisons of steady-state operating periods with different boundary conditions allow for a holistic analysis of the merit of the process control concept to optimize CLG process efficiency. During the 60 h of steady-state chemical looping operation investigated within this work, the process control concept was successfully applied for a total duration of ~35 h. Results of these endeavors are summarized in Fig. 8, showing the dependency of the AR recycling ratio and the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio in the AR. Here, two regions can clearly be observed. On the y-axis of Fig. 8, 78 operating sub-periods, for which flue gas recirculation in the AR were switched off, are visible. For the remaining 99 operating sub-periods, AR recycling ratios larger than zero were employed. Before AR flue gas recirculation was initiated (RR_{AR}=0), the pilot was operated with propane firing at different thermal loads in the AR for given operating periods. While propane injection was used to counter the high relative heat losses of the 1 MW_{th} pilot (10–15% of thermal input) for selected operating periods, (gaseous) fuel injection is commonly applied in DFBG applications as a mean of temperature control in both reactors (Ripfel-Nitsche et al., 2007; Bolhar-Nordenkamp et al., 2002; Bolhar-Nordenkamp et al., 2003), meaning that the deeper investigation of this measure on CLG efficiency provides further important insights.

3.2.1. Effect of process control concept on oxygen transport from AR to FR

Evaluation of all 177 operating sub-periods showed that for the given plant layout two options to control the oxygen transport to the FR exist. For the sub-periods, located on the y-axis of Fig. 8 (i.e. RR_{AR}=0), a clear dependency between λ_{AR,eff} and the propane input is visible. This indicates that in the case of significant propane injection in the AR, oxygen

uptake by the OC is impaired leading to lower values of λ_{AR,eff}. Since oxygen concentrations larger than 1 vol.-% were measured at the outlet of the AR for all operating periods with RR_{AR}=0 (see Fig. 9), the drop in the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio in the AR cannot be associated to thermodynamic constraints (i.e. enough oxygen for full-reoxidation of the OC was available inside the AR for all operating periods with RR_{AR}=0). This suggests that the injection of propane into the dense bed of the AR impairs the oxygen uptake of the OC kinetically (e.g. by leading to a reducing atmosphere in the dense bed, where gas-solid contacting is high), which is also supported by the fact that for RR_{AR}=0, the outlet AR O₂ concentration increases with decreasing λ_{AR,eff}. Regardless of the mechanism, this means that through propane injection, the OC behaves more and more as an “inert” inside the FR, as the OC enters the FR in a more reduced state, thus impairing reaction kinetics inside the FR. Ultimately, the control concept enforced by propane injection can thus be seen as a form of dual-fluidized bed

Fig. 10. Effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio in FR as a function of air-to-fuel equivalence ratio in AR for varying propane loads for all operating periods given in Table 4. The red shaded area indicates a deviation of 5% from the angle bisector.

Table 3

Oxidation degree (X_s) in% for all OC samples collected from LS4.1 and LS4.5 during operation.

Sample-#	Location	X _s [%]	ΔX _s [%]	Sampling Time
CLA1-S-10	LS4.1	104.4 ± 1.2	–	15:38 02.04.2022
CLA1-S-13	LS4.1	15.2 ± 0.6	–	05:30 03.04.2022
CLA1-S-42	LS4.1	94.6 ± 0.1	19.9 ± 0.3	03:30 10.04.2022
CLA1-S-43	LS4.5	74.7 ± 0.5	–	–
CLA1-S-49	LS4.1	86.7 ± 0.0	–	15:30 10.04.2022
CLA1-S-59	LS4.5	60.9 ± 0.2	20.4 ± 0.2	21:30 11.04.2022
CLA1-S-60	LS4.1	81.2 ± 0.3	–	–
CLA1-S-61	LS4.1	81.8 ± 0.1	16.0 ± 0.3	03:20 12.04.2022
CLA1-S-62	LS4.5	65.8 ± 0.4	–	–
CLA1-S-65	LS4.5	64.4 ± 0.6	19.3 ± 0.8	14:30 12.04.2022
CLA1-S-66	LS4.1	83.7 ± 1.1	–	–
CLA1-S-69	LS4.5	75.4 ± 0.9	14.9 ± 0.8	17:05 13.04.2022
CLA1-S-70	LS4.1	90.3 ± 0.8	–	–
CLA1-S-73	LS4.5	73.8 ± 0.9	17.3 ± 0.4	20:30 13.04.2022
CLA1-S-74	LS4.1	91.1 ± 0.0	–	–
CLA1-S-75	LS4.1	93.5 ± 0.1	14.8 ± 0.1	20:30 13.04.2022
CLA1-S-76	LS4.5	78.7 ± 0.1	–	–
CLA1-S-78	LS4.1	90.5 ± 0.2	13.7 ± 0.4	11:15 14.04.2022
CLA1-S-79	LS4.5	76.8 ± 0.7	–	–
CLA1-S-84	LS4.5	77.1 ± 0.5	13.1 ± 0.4	11:15 14.04.2022
CLA1-S-85	LS4.1	90.2 ± 0.4	–	–
CLA1-S-86	LS4.5	76.7 ± 0.1	10.3 ± 0.2	18:10 14.04.2022
CLA1-S-87	LS4.1	87.0 ± 0.2	–	–

gasification (DFBG), for which fuel introduction in the AR is used to drive up AR temperatures and thus obtain a driving force for the chemical reactions in the FR and an inert bed material is used to transport the reaction heat between the two reactors (Ripfel-Nitsche et al., 2007; Bolhar-Nordenkamp et al., 2002; Bolhar-Nordenkamp et al., 2003).

On the other hand, the desired effect on $\lambda_{AR,eff}$ is obtained by using the suggested process control concept, manipulating the AR recycling ratio at low propane input. For the given operating periods this translates into a drop of $\lambda_{AR,eff}$ from ~ 0.5 to ~ 0.2 as the AR recycling ratio is increased from 0 to 0.38. As elucidated in detail in Chapter 3.1, this can be explained by the fact that the oxygen uptake by the OC in the AR is diminished as the oxygen availability in the AR decreases. This lack in oxygen availability in the AR for $RR_{AR} > 0$ is also seen in Fig. 9, as outlet O_2 concentrations < 2 vol-% (generally < 1 vol-%) were measured for the AR, when the AR flue gas recirculation was switched-on ($RR_{AR} > 0.1$).

Efficient CLG operation is only obtained if the decrease in $\lambda_{AR,eff}$ with increasing RR_{AR} , also translates into a drop in the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio inside the FR. This is the case as $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ primarily governs the CLG process efficiency, by determining how much oxygen is released inside the FR, leading to a given degree of feedstock oxidation. To determine the correlation between the two effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratios, $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ and $\lambda_{AR,eff}$ are shown in Fig. 10 for all 177 operating sub-periods under investigation. It becomes clear that in case of low amounts of propane firing, all values fall onto or close to the angle bisector, signifying $\phi_\lambda = 1$.¹⁰ Thus, the CLG unit is in steady state for those operating conditions, and oxygen release in the FR is equal to the oxygen uptake in the AR, meaning that given sufficient stabilization times (see Chapter 3.1), a decrease in $\lambda_{AR,eff}$ also translates into an equivalent decrease in $\lambda_{FR,eff}$. However, as soon as propane loads exceed 150 kW, a clear upwards deviation from the angle bisector is visible, signifying that more oxygen is released in the FR than is taken up in the AR. This again underlines the previous hypothesis (see above), that in case of strong propane firing, oxygen uptake in the AR might be the rate-limiting step. This means when operating the CLG unit for long times with propane firing, the entire OC inventory slowly becomes more and more reduced until a new steady state is reached.¹¹ A finding supporting this hypothesis is that a solid sample taken from LS4.1 towards the end of BP6 (highlighted in Fig. 10) showed a strong degree of reduction (S-13: $X_{s,AR} = 15.2\%$, see Table 3 in the Appendix), when its oxidation degree was determined. Therefore, co-firing of propane or any other feedstock in the AR has to be considered undesired for CLG operation as it prevents meaningful oxygen transport from the AR to the FR. On the other hand, when striving for DFBG operation (i.e. no/limited oxygen transport) it yields the option to obtain a strongly reduced OC entering the FR, releasing low amounts of oxygen and potentially catalyzing certain chemical reactions (e.g. tar or methane reforming) (Zhou et al., 2022; Min et al., 2011). However, this approach is not considered further here, as efficient CLG operation, signified by meaningful oxygen transport between AR and FR, is targeted.

3.2.2. Acting mechanism of novel process control concept

Further insights into the underlying phenomena of the novel process control concept can be obtained when considering the oxidation degree of solid samples collected during different operating periods. As elaborated in Chapter 3.1, the pursued measure to obtain a more deeply reduced OC entering the FR is the restriction of air supply in the AR.

¹⁰ As explained above (see Chapter 3.1.2), measurement inaccuracy leads to minor deviations from $\phi_\lambda = 1$ for some operating points, although mass and component (C, H, O) balances could be closed with an accuracy of $\pm 5\%$ for all operating points.

¹¹ Within the entire duration of BP6 (> 7 h), steady-state conditions were not reached, meaning that the OC was further reduced throughout the entire duration.

Fig. 11. Oxidation degree of samples collected from LS4.1 as a function of the oxygen content at the AR outlet (for sampling times for the respective samples please refer to Table 3). Gray arrows denote the progression of $X_{s,AR}$ as RR_{AR} is increased.

Fig. 11, showing the dependency of the oxidation degree of samples collected from LS4.1 with the oxygen content at the AR outlet, displays a clear correlation between the two parameters. In case of oxygen excess ($x_{O_2,AR} > 3$ vol-%), full oxidation of the OC is achieved in the AR (for low amounts of propane firing). Yet, with decreasing oxygen content at the AR outlet, $X_{s,AR}$ drops to a value of approx. 90% at $x_{O_2,AR} = 0$ vol-%, indicating that OC oxidation kinetics play a crucial role inside the AR at low oxygen concentrations. When further decreasing the oxygen input at $x_{O_2,AR} = 0$ vol-% through increasing RR_{AR} , the oxidation degree of the OC further decreases, as its oxidation is hindered through thermodynamic constraints. Consequently, the application of flue gas recirculation for the AR is an efficient measure to prevent full OC oxidation in the AR. As mentioned before, another approach to achieve this is the injection of significant amounts of propane into the AR, as practiced during BP6. Fig. 15 shows that as an effect of continuous propane-induced oxygen depletion of the OC during BP6 (see also Fig. 10), the OC sample collected from LS4.1 towards the end of BP6 exhibited a close to fully reduced state. Therefore, the solid sample corroborates the previous hypothesis that propane injection hinders oxygen uptake inside the AR. Moreover, it can be postulated that the OC was further reduced with each redox cycle, as more oxygen was released inside the FR than taken up inside the AR during BP6 (see Fig. 10), requiring a given time until the entire OC inventory was reduced to $X_{s,AR} < 20\%$. This would also explain why the 21 sub-periods of BP6 fall onto a line rather than an individual point in Fig. 10 and Fig. 15 (see Chapter 3.2.3) as the OC was continuously reduced further throughout the entire length of BP6 (> 7 h). This finding makes another strong point for using the suggested process control strategy, relying on AR flue gas recirculation, to control the degree of oxidation of the OC at the AR outlet, as opposed to propane injection - while rapid and tailored adjustments of the system are attainable for the former, extensive stabilization times are necessary for the latter.

Ultimately, the decrease in $X_{s,AR}$ obtained for either approach only yields the desired result (i.e. an increase in the CGE), if oxygen release in the FR is reduced. As explained before, this means that the change in oxidation degree between AR and FR and thus the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio have to be reduced for a given solid circulation rate (see Eq. (16)). It is known that as $X_{s,AR}$ is reduced (e.g. through oxygen restriction in the AR), the propensity of the OC to release oxygen inside the FR is reduced (Abad et al., 2011; Ohlemuller et al., 2018). The ensuing slower reaction kinetics, thus ultimately lead to an increase in the CGE, as the feedstock is oxidized to lesser extents inside the FR. This

Fig. 12. Change in oxidation degree between AR and FR determined for samples collected from LS4.1 & LS4.5 and efficient AR air-to-fuel equivalence ratio as a function of AR oxidation degree (for sampling times for the respective solid samples refer to Table 3).

Fig. 13. Schematic illustration of the suggested mechanism of action of the CLG process control concept - Effect of an increase in the AR recycling ratio ($RR_{AR} \uparrow$) on important process variables.

correlation is illustrated in Fig. 12, showing a distinct impact of $X_{s,AR}$ on ΔX_s and $\lambda_{AR,eff}$. However, it becomes visible, that the oxidation degree at the AR outlet is not the only variable affecting the oxygen release inside the FR. For BP10, 12, 13, 15, and 16 for which FR temperatures fell into the range of 820–890 °C, significantly higher values were obtained for ΔX_s and $\lambda_{AR,eff}$ for a given value of $X_{s,AR}$ than for BP23, 24, 25, 27, 29, and 30, for which FR temperatures were below 800 °C. This can be related to the fact, that apart from X_s , the FR temperature is another crucial parameter affecting OC reaction kinetics (Abad et al., 2011; Ohlemüller et al., 2018). Consequently, one has to consider this active feedback loop between $X_{s,AR}$, ΔX_s , and T_{FR} , when attempting to explain the behavior of the CLG unit during the transient switch-over periods.

To further understand this, the entire mechanism of action proposed for the CLG process control concept, which is illustrated in Fig. 13, has to be considered. As explained above, the oxygen release inside the FR is kinetically limited for the 1 MW_{th} unit, and is thus dependent on the oxidation degree of the OC entering the FR ($X_{s,AR}$), FR temperatures, and the solids residence time inside the FR ($\tau_{s,FR}$). Subsequent to the increase in RR_{AR} , entailing a decrease in the oxygen content in the AR, $X_{s,AR}$ decreases. This parameter being one factor impacting OC kinetics, thus

Fig. 14. AR (top) and FR (bottom) reactor temperatures as a function of the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio for different thermal loads for all operating periods given in Table 4. Gray markup to guide the eye: Straight lines mark the effect of λ_{eff} on reactor temperatures, whereas arrows mark the effect of increasing total thermal loads.

Fig. 15. Cold gas efficiency as a function of the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio in the FR for varying AR carbon conversions for all operating periods given in Table 4. Gray markup to guide the eye: Straight lines mark the effect of $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ on the cold gas efficiency, whereas arrows mark the effect of increasing $X_{C,FR}$ (=decreasing $X_{C,AR}$).

leads to a drop in the oxygen release in the FR (i.e. ΔX_s , $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ and $\lambda_{AR,eff}$ decrease¹²). Due to this, the enthalpy of reaction (i.e. ΔH) of the entire system decreases, as exothermic oxidation reactions occur to lesser extents inside the FR and AR. As a result of this, reactor temperatures decrease (see Fig. 5 in Chapter 3.1.1 and Fig. 14 in Chapter 3.2.3), which again leads to slower OC reaction kinetics and thus a decrease in oxygen release inside the FR. The time required for this active feedback loop between OC reaction kinetics, reactor enthalpies, and reactor temperatures to stabilize, can be named as another factor playing into the

¹² Fig. 12 and Fig. 19 (see appendix) show a close correlation between ΔX_s and $\lambda_{AR,eff}$, demonstrating that the decrease in oxygen release in the FR and uptake in the AR ($\lambda_{FR,eff}$ and $\lambda_{AR,eff}$), which can be derived from the FR and AR uptake and gas composition, is also clearly visible in the solids composition (ΔX_s).

transient behavior of the CLG unit after changes of RR_{AR} . Clearly, the duration required for this feedback loop to stabilize depends on several factors, such as the size of the reactor inventory (i.e. total OC mass), the interplay of gas-phase and refractory temperatures (T_{RL}),¹³ as well as the extent to which the oxygen availability inside the AR is reduced, explaining why the duration required to reach steady state varied for TP-1, TP-2, and TP-3 (2–4 h).

On the one hand, the inclusion of data collected from the solid samples thus corroborate all fundamental hypotheses derived from on-line data, such as the fact that changes in the oxidation degree of the OC, induced through reduced oxygen availability in the AR, are responsible for the increased CGE of the CLG unit. On the other hand, the combined analysis of online and offline data collected for different steady state CLG operating periods allowed for deeper insights into the mechanisms occurring inside the CLG unit, further promoting the understanding of the novel gasification technology.

3.2.3. Effect of novel process control concept on CLG process efficiency

After presenting the acting mechanism of the novel process control concept, the question is how it affects the overall efficiency of the process. When evaluating CLG efficiency in the 1 MW_{th} scale, it has to be kept in mind that in contrast to other units, a free variation of individual parameters is not possible, due to the entanglement of hydrodynamics, product and educt compositions, reaction kinetics, temperatures, etc. One important example for this is given in Fig. 14. Here, it becomes obvious that in chemical looping mode the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratios primarily determine reactor temperatures.¹⁴ This can be related to the fact that depending on the oxygen release (FR) and uptake (AR), the exothermicity of the chemical reactions vary, leading to changes in reactor temperatures, which was already observed in Chapter 3.1. As it is known that changes in FR temperatures affect the CLG efficiency (Condori et al., 2021a,b, 2022), this means that altering $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ impacts CLG efficiency directly (i.e. through reduced oxygen release) as well as indirectly (i.e. via decreasing FR temperatures). Another effect visible in Fig. 14 is that higher reactor temperatures are generally attainable for given air-to-fuel equivalence ratios by increasing the total thermal input. Again this observation can be explained by considering the heat balance of the system, as for higher thermal loads, the relative impact of heat losses from the reactor walls as well as the cooling effect of the cooling lances decreases and hence higher reactor temperatures can be sustained.

These observations ultimately underline an inherent trade-off also faced in full-scale units: Although higher reactor temperatures are generally preferable (esp. for reaction kinetics), they also mean that higher air-to-fuel equivalence ratios are required, lowering key performance indicators such as the cold gas efficiency of the process. Therefore, there exists a “sweet spot” for which reactor temperatures are sufficiently high to drive the underlying chemical reactions, yet air-to-fuel equivalence ratios are low enough to obtain meaningful CGEs (see below). However, when extrapolating these results to a full-scale gasifier, the following peculiarities of the 1 MW_{th} pilot have to be factored-in:

- i Because of the high surface-to-volume ratio of the pilot plant, heat losses amount to approx. 10–15% of the thermal input, reducing the amount of energy available for the chemical reactions.

¹³ As elaborated in Chapter 3.1, the interplay between reactor gas phase temperatures and refractory lining temperatures decelerates rapid temperature drops/increases, esp. for reactors with a high surface-to-volume ratio.

¹⁴ In an autothermal setup reactor temperatures are dependent on the entire set of boundary conditions (see also Fig. 13). Apart from the efficient air-to-fuel equivalence ratio and the thermal load highlighted in Fig. 14, this includes solid circulation, the amount of gas used for fluidization, and heat losses, amongst others (Dieringer et al., Jun. 2020).

- ii Due to the setup of the reactor system, the cooling lances in the AR cannot be fully removed from the pilot plant and hence continuously extract heat from the reactor system. For the given operating periods, heat extraction via those cooling lances amounts to 7–11% of the thermal input, further reducing the energy available for chemical reactions.¹⁵
- iii Due to i. and ii., reactor temperatures in the 1 MW_{th} unit are lower than in an industrial setup for a given set of boundary conditions. Hence, reaction kinetics are slower, leading to lower feedstock conversions inside the FR and ultimately to lower overall efficiencies.
- iv The calculation of the cold gas efficiency (see Eq. (7)) neglects all hydrocarbons except for methane (i.e. $C \geq 2$). This means the energy contained in these species is not represented in the cold gas efficiency.

Therefore, when operating an industry-scale chemical looping gasifier autothermally and when considering the full heating value of the FR product gas, process simulations show that cold gas efficiencies well above 60% can be expected at FR temperatures above 850 °C and air-to-fuel equivalence ratios around 0.3 (Dieringer et al., 2020; Samprón et al., 2021). Due to the peculiarities of the 1 MW_{th} unit, values for the CGE obtained here fall short of this value. Nonetheless, the analysis of the impact of important process variables on the cold gas efficiency in the 1 MW_{th} unit yields unique insights, regardless of the absolute value obtained, due to the industry-like setup of the CLG system.

Previous studies found that for externally heated CLG units, the most important variable affecting the CGE is the efficient FR air-to-fuel equivalence ratio (Condori et al., 2021a; Condori et al., 2022). The dependency for those two parameters obtained for the 1 MW_{th} pilot plant is shown in Fig. 15. As expected, the cold gas efficiency increases with decreasing $\lambda_{FR,eff}$. As less oxygen is released in the FR, leading to an increase in the heating value of the FR product gasses, supporting the findings made in Chapter 3.1. For the operating periods under investigation, the cold gas efficiency increases from 20% to above 35% when decreasing $\lambda_{FR,eff}$ from 0.4 to 0.2 by using AR flue gas recirculation.

A second trend visible in Fig. 15 is that η_{CGE} increases with decreasing carbon conversion in the AR. This means that as the feedstock is converted to a greater degree inside the FR ($X_{C,AR} \downarrow$ & $X_{C,FR} \uparrow$, see Eq. (10)), more gas or gas with a higher heating value is obtained from the FR. Strategies to increase char conversion inside the FR are for example increased FR temperatures [(Cetin et al., 2005; Barrio and Hustad, 2001; Barrio et al., 2001; Keller et al., 2011; DIRECTIVE (EU) 1997; Ollero et al., 2003)], an increase in residence times of all solids in the FR (e.g. higher reactor inventories or alternative FR layout) (Condori et al., 2022; Pérez-Vega et al., 2016), or an exclusive increase in char residence times in the FR, e.g. via intermediate char separation and reintroduction in a so-called carbon stripper (Pérez-Vega et al., 2016; Abad et al., 2013; Abad et al., 2015). Yet, for a given reactor layout, optimizing char conversion inside the FR without jeopardizing the cold gas efficiency is not easily done, due to the system’s entanglement. One example for this being that higher FR char conversions were generally obtained at higher FR temperatures. However, as shown in Fig. 14, these are obtained for higher values of $\lambda_{FR,eff}$, for which lower CGEs are obtained (see Fig. 15), thus signifying an additional trade-off, which needs to be optimized to increase process efficiency. Another interesting trend visible in Fig. 15, which was observed towards the end of BP-6, where large amounts of propane were fired (see Fig. 10), is that the cold gas efficiency increases slightly as the effective air-to-fuel equivalence ratio increases between BP6–14 and BP6–19. To this point, it is unclear why

¹⁵ This circumstance is accounted for in the calculation of the CGE, yet clearly still impacts reactor temperatures.

this behavior was observed. Yet, this again indicates that at very low OC oxidation degrees,¹⁶ the OC could catalyze endothermic gas phase reactions (e.g. tar/methane reforming), thereby increasing the energy content of the FR product gas. The catalytic effect of reduced ilmenite on different reactions has also been observed in literature (Zhou et al., 2022; Min et al., 2011). Hence, the results presented in Fig. 15 suggest that lower air-to-fuel equivalence ratios in the FR could enhance cold gas efficiencies of the CLG process not only by lowering the oxygen release in the FR, but also by catalyzing endothermic gas-phase reactions, favoring the formation of syngas species, through the presence of a more reduced OC inside the FR at lower values of $\lambda_{FR,eff}$. This hypothesis needs to be confirmed by further studies, e.g. measurements of higher hydrocarbons.

4. Conclusions

One crucial aspect in up-scaling the CLG technology is the demonstration of a viable process control concept, allowing for autothermal operation. In the course of this work, it has been shown that the suggested process control concept, utilizing AR flue gas recirculation to restrict the air supply in the AR, allows for an independent control of reactor hydrodynamics and the air-to-fuel equivalence ratio of the CLG process, forming the basis for efficient CLG operation. Based on experimental results gathered in 1 MW_{th} scale, the following conclusions can be made:

- The presented CLG concept satisfies all relevant criteria, i.e. facilitating the production of a high-calorific raw synthesis gas through guaranteeing sufficiently high temperatures in the FR, without jeopardizing the chemical energy contained in the feedstock.
- The selected route of implementation, i.e. flue gas recycling for the AR, showed promising results during the 1 MW_{th} test campaigns, as the oxygen input was controlled accurately, without disturbing reactor hydrodynamics on thus, solid and heat transport between the reactors.
- Other process-wise implementation options, such as diluting the inlet air for the AR with an inert (e.g. N₂) or tailoring AR dimensions, briefly described in this paper, should show similar results and can be employed, depending on their suitability for the given plant layout. Hence, the general control concept of reducing the air-to-fuel equivalence ratio (λ) is suitable for large-scale (>100 MW_{th}) CLG units.
- Experimental data shows, that changes in λ propagate slowly into the system. This considerable inertia of the system is caused by the fact that the OC inventory of the gasifier effectively acts as an oxygen storage, releasing surplus oxygen during the transient adjustment process. Moreover, the interplay of reactor temperatures, OC reaction kinetics and reaction enthalpies is deemed to play a crucial role in the system's transient response. For the 1 MW_{th} unit, switch-over times of up to 4 h were observed when reducing λ through initiating flue gas recycling inside the AR. Consequently, this system inertia has to be considered, when operating CLG units of substantial size.
- Qualitative and quantitative comparisons between different transient switch-over periods showed that the observed behavior occurs consistently regardless of the exact boundary conditions, indicating that the observed transient behavior is a key aspect in operation of large-scale CLG units.

- Through analysis of solid OC samples extracted from both loop seals during operation, the postulated progression of the oxidation degree of the OC during the transient switch-over periods was verified. With the inclusion of this data set, a detailed mechanism of action of the CLG process control concept was formulated.

In summary, the results presented in this paper provide a comprehensive understanding of the CLG technology and its governing phenomena and thus can be considered to be a crucial building block in advancing it towards market maturity. To further extend process understanding and to be able to further refine the process control concept, it is foreseen to apply it to concept to reach lower λ (0.35–0.45) at thermal loads up to 1.5 MW_{th}, to increase the cold gas efficiency in semi-industrial scale, further underlining the competitiveness of the CLG technology.

Author contribution

Paul Dieringer: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft, Visualization. **Falko Marx:** Writing – Review & Editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation. **Benjamin Michel:** Investigation. **Jochen Ströhle:** Writing – Review & Editing, Supervision, Project Administration, Funding Acquisition. **Bernd Eppler:** Resources, Funding Acquisition.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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¹⁶ As stated in Chapter 3.2.2, low values for X_S were found to be present toward the end of BP-6, associated to the prolonged duration of oxygen depletion during BP-6, see Fig. 10 & Fig. 11.

Annex 1. Additional Information

A.1. Derivation of calculation for AR recycling ratio (RR_{AR})

The calculation of RR_{AR} is achieved by calculating a component balance (C or O) around the primary-air line (system boundaries, see Fig. 16).

As the only unit operation taking place inside these system boundaries is the mixing of the recycled AR flue gas and fresh air, the total mass and thus volume flow stays constant:

$$\dot{V}_{in,AR} = \dot{V}_{Rec.,AR} + \dot{V}_{Air,AR} \tag{17}$$

i) Oxygen Balance

The oxygen balance around the primary-air line thus can be formulated as:

$$\dot{V}_{in,AR} \cdot x_{O_2,AR,in} = \dot{V}_{Rec.,AR} \cdot x_{O_2,AR,out} + \dot{V}_{Air,AR} \cdot 21 \text{ vol.}\% \tag{18}$$

With consideration of Eq. (17), Eq. (18) can be formulated as:

$$\dot{V}_{in,AR} \cdot x_{O_2,AR,in} = (\dot{V}_{in,AR} - \dot{V}_{Air,AR}) \cdot x_{O_2,AR,out} + \dot{V}_{Air,AR} \cdot 21 \text{ vol.}\% \tag{19}$$

Reordering of Eq. (19) yields:

$$\dot{V}_{Air,AR} = \dot{V}_{in,AR} \cdot \frac{x_{O_2,AR,in} - x_{O_2,AR,out}}{21 \text{ vol.}\% - x_{O_2,AR,out}} \tag{20}$$

Combination of Eq. (5), Eq. (17), and Eq. (18) thus results in:

$$RR_{AR} = \frac{\dot{V}_{Rec.,AR}}{\dot{V}_{Rec.,AR} + \dot{V}_{Air,AR}} = \frac{\dot{V}_{in,AR} - \dot{V}_{in,AR} \cdot \frac{x_{O_2,AR,in} - x_{O_2,AR,out}}{21 \text{ vol.}\% - x_{O_2,AR,out}}}{\dot{V}_{in,AR}} = \frac{x_{O_2,AR,in} - 21 \text{ vol.}\%}{x_{O_2,AR,out} - 21 \text{ vol.}\%} \tag{21}$$

If the desired CLG operation is achieved, the outlet O_2 concentration for the AR drops to 0 vol-%, and Eq. (21), simplifies to:

$$RR_{AR} = \frac{x_{O_2,AR,in} - 21 \text{ vol.}\%}{-21 \text{ vol.}\%} \tag{22}$$

ii) Carbon Balance

For the carbon balance, it is assumed that the CO_2 content of ambient air can be neglected:

$$\dot{V}_{in,AR} \cdot x_{CO_2,AR,in} = \dot{V}_{Rec.,AR} \cdot x_{CO_2,AR,out} \tag{23}$$

Combination of Eq. (5), and Eq. (23) thus results in:

$$RR_{AR} = \frac{x_{CO_2,AR,in}}{x_{CO_2,AR,out}} \tag{24}$$

Fig. 16. Illustration of CLG control concept utilized in 1 MW_{th} pilot plant with system boundary (dashed line) and all variables (grey arrows) used for derivation of AR recycling.

A.2. Progression of Evaluation Parameters during TP-2 & TP-3

Fig. 17 and Fig. 18 show the progression of the most important evaluation parameters for the transient periods TP-2 and TP-3, respectively. It is visible that for all three transient periods similar observations can be made. These are presented in detail in Chapter 3.1.

A.3. Oxidation degree of OC samples collected during 1 MW_{th} operation

Table 3 shows a summary of the oxidation degrees (X_S) of all loop seal samples collected during CLG operation, with the corresponding sampling location and time. The change in oxidation degree between AR and FR (ΔX_S) for those solid samples is visualized as a function of the efficient AR air-to-fuel equivalence ratio in Fig. 19.

A.4. Boundary conditions of operating periods under consideration

The boundary conditions for each steady-state operating point under consideration are listed in Table 4, while boundary conditions for the transient periods are given in Table 5.

Fig. 17. Progression of important process and evaluation parameters over time for TP-2.

From top to bottom: a.) FR and b.) AR temperature, c.) cold gas efficiency (η_{CGE}), d.) H₂/CO-ratio in FR product gas, e.) oxygen concentration at AR outlet ($x_{O_2,AR,out}$), f.) air-to-fuel equivalence ratio (λ), g.) oxygen concentration at AR inlet ($x_{O_2,AR,in}$), h.) AR gas velocity, and i.) AR flue gas recycling ratio (RR_{AR}), calculated from O₂ (-) and CO₂ (:) balance. Arrows with diamonds at the end signify the sampling time of a given solid sample.

Fig. 18. Progression of important process and evaluation parameters over time for TP-3. From top to bottom: a.) FR and b.) AR temperature, c.) cold gas efficiency (η_{CGE}), d.) H_2/CO -ratio in FR product gas, e.) oxygen concentration at AR outlet ($x_{O_2,AR,out}$), f.) air-to-fuel equivalence ratio (λ), g.) oxygen concentration at AR inlet ($x_{O_2,AR,in}$), h.) AR gas velocity, and i.) AR flue gas recycling ratio (RR_{AR}), calculated from O_2 (-) and CO_2 (:) balance. Arrows with diamonds at the end signify the sampling time of a given solid sample.

Fig. 19. Correlation between the measured efficient AR air-to-fuel equivalence ratio and the oxidation degree between AR and FR determined for samples collected from LS4.1 & LS4.5.

Table 4
Operating conditions for steady-state operating periods under investigation. BPX (steady-state operating period).

Variable	Description	BP1	BP2	BP3	BP4	BP5	BP6	BP7	Unit
$m_{Feedstock}$	Mass flow of biomass pellets to FR	156.1	167.5	163.4	175.4	190.3	191.5	223.2	kg/h
$m_{Make-Up}$	Mass flow of OC to LS4.1	34.7	88.4	68.2	56.6	0.0	41.9	0.0	kg/h
T_{AR}	AR max. temperature	898.6	885.2	879.3	884.8	843.6	877.2	958.6	°C
T_{FR}	FR max. temperature	812.2	820.9	821.7	821.9	756.7	772.9	858.9	°C
ΔP_{AR}	AR pressure drop (inventory)	21.5	32.9	44.4	39.5	29.0	32.8	41.7	mbar
$P_{AR,Cyclone}$	Pressure downstream of AR cyclone	-3.1	-3.1	-3.1	-3.1	-3.1	-3.1	-1.0	mbar
ΔP_{FR}	FR pressure drop (inventory)	37.5	45.9	49.5	50.3	65.1	65.8	70.6	mbar
$P_{FR,Cyclone}$	Pressure downstream of FR cyclone	5.5	5.4	5.5	5.6	5.1	5.2	7.4	mbar
$m_{FM,FR}$	Mass flow of FR fluidization (H ₂ O)	304.8	306.0	301.6	297.2	249.8	253.7	237.7	kg/h
$m_{FM,AR}^*$	Mass flow of AR fluidization*	953.7	952.3	952.1	953.9	932.5	921.7	1004.8	kg/h
$m_{C3H8,AR}$	Mass flow of propane entering AR	16.6	18.3	19.4	19.4	19.4	19.4	8.6	kg/h
$m_{FM,LS4.1}$	Vol. flow of LS4.1 fluidization	19.2 (N ₂)	19.3 (N ₂)	19.2 (N ₂)	19.4 (N ₂)	20.5 (N ₂)	22 (N ₂)	16 (N ₂)	Nm ³ /h
$m_{FM,LS4.5}$	Vol. flow of LS4.5 fluidization	26.7 (N ₂)	29.2 (N ₂)	29.9 (N ₂)	30.8 (N ₂)	30.4 (N ₂)	31 (N ₂)	20.6 (CO ₂)	Nm ³ /h
$m_{FM,J-Valve}$	Vol. flow of J-Valve fluidization	13.4 (N ₂)	15.7 (N ₂)	16.8 (N ₂)	16.9 (N ₂)	18.3 (N ₂)	18.1 (CO ₂)	18.4 (N ₂)	Nm ³ /h
RR_{AR}	AR flue gas recycling ratio	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	-

Variable	Description	BP8	BP9	BP10	BP11	BP12	BP13	BP14	BP15	Unit
$m_{Feedstock}$	Mass flow of biomass pellets to FR	222.8	223.6	226.4	220.8	231.8	226.4	235.0	229.1	kg/h
$m_{Make-Up}$	Mass flow of OC to LS4.1	0.0	33.2	35.3	24.9	46.1	53.8	0.0	50.9	kg/h
T_{AR}	AR max. temperature	957.9	963.1	974.5	992.6	943.3	948.0	919.8	911.6	°C
T_{FR}	FR max. temperature	858.7	869.0	892.3	908.7	864.6	881.4	839.5	833.6	°C
ΔP_{AR}	AR pressure drop (inventory)	37.8	45.0	52.0	48.7	47.3	39.8	55.4	53.7	mbar
$P_{AR,Cyclone}$	Pressure downstream of AR cyclone	-1.0	-1.0	-1.0	-1.0	-1.1	-1.1	-0.9	-0.9	mbar
ΔP_{FR}	FR pressure drop (inventory)	69.6	61.4	68.0	66.4	70.6	69.3	75.9	73.4	mbar
$P_{FR,Cyclone}$	Pressure downstream of FR cyclone	7.8	7.2	7.6	5.8	6.8	7.2	5.1	5.2	mbar
$m_{FM,FR}$	Mass flow of FR fluidization (H ₂ O)	239.1	232.1	227.0	229.9	230.9	235.7	216.8	217.9	kg/h
$m_{FM,AR}^*$	Mass flow of AR fluidization*	1005.7	965.6	965.6	966.2	970.2	1000.6	969.4	971.0	kg/h
$m_{C3H8,AR}$	Mass flow of propane entering AR	8.6	10.1	10.1	10.1	10.1	10.1	6.8	3.6	kg/h
$m_{FM,LS4.1}$	Vol. flow of LS4.1 fluidization	15.9 (N ₂)	15.7 (N ₂)	15.1 (N ₂)	14.9 (N ₂)	15.6 (N ₂)	15.2 (N ₂)	15.7 (N ₂)	15.6 (N ₂)	Nm ³ /h
$m_{FM,LS4.5}$	Vol. flow of LS4.5 fluidization	19.6 (CO ₂)	18.8 (CO ₂)	19.5 (CO ₂)	19.1 (CO ₂)	19.3 (CO ₂)	16.5 (CO ₂)	14.9 (CO ₂)	15.3 (CO ₂)	Nm ³ /h
$m_{FM,J-Valve}$	Vol. flow of J-Valve fluidization	20.9 (CO ₂)	21.8 (CO ₂)	22 (CO ₂)	22 (CO ₂)	22.9 (CO ₂)	23.7 (CO ₂)	19.5 (CO ₂)	18.9 (CO ₂)	Nm ³ /h
RR_{AR}	AR flue gas recycling ratio	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.00	0.23	0.24	-

Variable	Description	BP16	BP17	BP18	BP19	BP20	BP21	BP22	BP23	Unit
$m_{Feedstock}$	Mass flow of biomass pellets to FR	221.3	223.7	221.5	228.9	228.9	230.2	226.6	232.5	kg/h
$m_{Make-Up}$	Mass flow of OC to LS4.1	0.0	1.7	0.0	0.0	23.2	91.8	0.0	13.0	kg/h
T_{AR}	AR max. temperature	906.2	904.0	903.3	902.2	893.8	884.4	883.7	882.1	°C
T_{FR}	FR max. temperature	821.7	821.3	816.0	814.2	808.8	806.6	800.5	792.9	°C
ΔP_{AR}	AR pressure drop (inventory)	44.0	42.3	47.2	45.2	47.6	56.5	64.4	63.8	mbar
$P_{AR,Cyclone}$	Pressure downstream of AR cyclone	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1	-1.1	-1.2	-1.2	mbar
ΔP_{FR}	FR pressure drop (inventory)	90.0	91.0	77.8	74.7	74.2	73.5	65.2	63.5	mbar
$P_{FR,Cyclone}$	Pressure downstream of FR cyclone	7.4	6.9	7.0	8.1	6.4	7.3	7.2	7.1	mbar
$m_{FM,FR}$	Mass flow of FR fluidization (H ₂ O)	186.5	183.7	164.7	181.8	183.8	193.8	195.8	197.3	kg/h
$m_{FM,AR}^*$	Mass flow of AR fluidization*	972.8	968.2	928.2	929.3	928.2	969.3	933.1	927.2	kg/h
$m_{C3H8,AR}$	Mass flow of propane entering AR	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.4	7.2	5.4	5.4	kg/h
$m_{FM,LS4.1}$	Vol. flow of LS4.1 fluidization	15 (N ₂)	15 (N ₂)	15.2 (N ₂)	15.3 (N ₂)	15.2 (N ₂)	16 (N ₂)	16 (N ₂)	16.1 (N ₂)	Nm ³ /h
$m_{FM,LS4.5}$	Vol. flow of LS4.5 fluidization	14.9 (CO ₂)	14.8 (CO ₂)	15.7 (CO ₂)	15.5 (CO ₂)	15.8 (CO ₂)	20.3 (N ₂)	20.6 (N ₂)	20.5 (N ₂)	Nm ³ /h
$m_{FM,J-Valve}$	Vol. flow of J-Valve fluidization	11.8 (CO ₂)	11.6 (CO ₂)	11.6 (CO ₂)	11.6 (CO ₂)	12.4 (CO ₂)	14.7 (CO ₂)	13.3 (CO ₂)	12.5 (CO ₂)	Nm ³ /h
RR_{AR}	AR flue gas recycling ratio	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.24	0.24	0.24	-

Variable	Description	BP24	BP25	BP26	BP27	BP28	BP29	BP30	Unit
$m_{Feedstock}$	Mass flow of biomass pellets to FR	229.8	228.9	213.7	209.5	209.6	221.9	238.8	kg/h
$m_{Make-Up}$	Mass flow of OC to LS4.1	0.0	10.6	20.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.5	kg/h
T_{AR}	AR max. temperature	882.5	868.6	844.0	840.7	834.0	833.0	797.3	°C
T_{FR}	FR max. temperature	794.4	788.9	757.7	746.0	730.3	725.4	722.8	°C
ΔP_{AR}	AR pressure drop (inventory)	64.5	64.0	63.4	56.0	50.8	49.0	74.3	mbar
$P_{AR,Cyclone}$	Pressure downstream of AR cyclone	-1.1	-1.0	-1.0	-1.0	-1.0	-1.0	-0.8	mbar
ΔP_{FR}	FR pressure drop (inventory)	65.5	76.8	106.7	124.7	134.3	135.6	65.0	mbar
$P_{FR,Cyclone}$	Pressure downstream of FR cyclone	7.6	7.2	7.4	7.1	7.0	7.1	7.0	mbar
$m_{FM,FR}$	Mass flow of FR fluidization (H ₂ O)	196.4	200.6	200.9	203.0	203.2	204.3	251.1	kg/h
$m_{FM,AR}^*$	Mass flow of AR fluidization*	927.2	944.7	952.1	953.5	956.5	957.3	960.4	kg/h
$m_{C3H8,AR}$	Mass flow of propane entering AR	5.4	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	kg/h
$m_{FM,LS4.1}$	Vol. flow of LS4.1 fluidization	16.1 (N ₂)	16.5 (N ₂)	16.7 (N ₂)	16.7 (N ₂)	16.8 (N ₂)	16.9 (N ₂)	17.7 (N ₂)	Nm ³ /h
$m_{FM,LS4.5}$	Vol. flow of LS4.5 fluidization	20.1 (N ₂)	18.9 (N ₂)	16.1 (CO ₂)	16.3 (CO ₂)	16.1 (CO ₂)	16.4 (CO ₂)	16.8 (CO ₂)	Nm ³ /h
$m_{FM,J-Valve}$	Vol. flow of J-Valve fluidization	12.5 (CO ₂)	18.4 (CO ₂)	19.4 (CO ₂)	19.8 (CO ₂)	20.1 (CO ₂)	20.9 (CO ₂)	21.8 (CO ₂)	Nm ³ /h
RR_{AR}	AR flue gas recycling ratio	0.23	0.23	0.32	0.32	0.35	0.34	0.37	-

* AR fluidization medium: pure air or mixture of air & AR recycled flue gas.

Table 5

Operating conditions for the transient operating periods under investigation. TP-X (Transient Period).

Variable	Description	TP-1	TP-2	TP-3	Unit
$\dot{m}_{Feedstock}$	Mass flow of biomass pellets to FR	227.6	234.9	223.3	kg/h
$\dot{m}_{Make-Up}$	Mass flow of OC to LS4.1	44.4	37.4	10.8	kg/h
T_{AR}	AR max. temperature	973.1	918.5	914.1	°C
T_{FR}	FR max. temperature	889.9	842.2	835.2	°C
ΔP_{AR}	AR pressure drop (inventory)	48.6	56.1	46.8	mbar
$P_{AR,Cyclone}$	Pressure downstream of AR cyclone	-1.0	-1.0	-1.1	mbar
ΔP_{FR}	FR pressure drop (inventory)	68.0	70.3	87.6	mbar
$P_{FR,Cyclone}$	Pressure downstream of FR cyclone	7.2	5.2	7.1	mbar
$\dot{m}_{FM,FR}$	Mass flow of FR fluidization (H ₂ O)	239.5	239.7	217.1	kg/h
$\dot{m}_{FM,AR}$	Mass flow of AR fluidization*	968.4	950.3	971.3	kg/h
$\dot{m}_{C3H8,AR}$	Mass flow of propane entering AR	10.1	6.8	7.7	kg/h
$\dot{m}_{FM,LS4.1}$	Vol. flow of LS4.1 fluidization	15.2 (N ₂)	15.4 (N ₂)	14.8 (N ₂)	Nm ³ /h
$\dot{m}_{FM,LS4.5}$	Vol. flow of LS4.5 fluidization	22.4 (CO ₂)	14.8 (CO ₂)	16.5 (CO ₂)	Nm ³ /h
$\dot{m}_{FM,J-Valve}$	Vol. flow of J-Valve fluidization	19.6 (CO ₂)	19.8 (CO ₂)	15.6 (CO ₂)	Nm ³ /h

* AR fluidization medium: pure air or mixture of air & recycled AR flue gas.

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